

1. Response of observed and simulated grain yield of rice to competition from different densities of weeds (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) emerging at different times. IRRI, 1994-95.

2. Comparison between simulated and observed dry matter of rice from transplanting to maturity. In the legend, ds and ws = crop seasons (dry and wet), H and L = weed densities (high [40], and low [20] plants m⁻²) 1 and 2 = time of weed emergence (1 = early [2-5 DAT], 2 = late [12-15 DAT]). IRRI, 1994-95.

treatments, suggesting a need to further evaluate the model's ability to predict LAI.

Dry matter production and grain yield (Fig. 1) were significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced by competition from early-emerging weeds. Reduction was greater at high than at low weed density. Simulated and observed grain yields across all weed densities and time of weed emergence treatment combinations were highly correlated ($R = 0.97^{**}$) and did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$). Simulated and observed dry matter content from transplanting to maturity were also correlated ($R = 0.92^{**}$) (Fig. 2).

INTERCOM can provide insights into the effects of *Echinochloa* competition on rice when the crop receives adequate N, irrespective of time of weed flush or weed density. ■

Weed control in direct seeded puddled rice

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Weed control in direct seeded rice is a serious problem in northern India. Manual weeding controls weeds effectively but availability and cost of labor limit its adoption. There are safe and nonphytotoxic herbicides, but their effectiveness has not yet been evaluated.

Butachlor, pendimethalin, and thio-bencarb are the recommended herbicides, but at least one additional hand weeding is required with these. The use of safener, an antiphytotoxicity compound that eliminates the toxic effect of herbicides on rice seedlings, offers opportunities to control

Effect of herbicides and cultural methods on grain yield, panicles m⁻², panicle weight, and weed dry weight in direct-seeded puddled rice. Pantnagar, India, 1993-94.

Treatment	Time of application (DAS) ^a	Dose (kg ai ha ⁻¹)	Concentration	1993				1994			
				Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)
					No. m ⁻²	Weight (g)			No. m ⁻²	Weight (g)	
Weed-free (check)	-	-	-	5.3	475	1.42	10	5.9	468	1.05	35
Hand weeding twice	20 and 40	-	-	5.1	357	1.66	91	5.4	486	1.18	175
High plant population (125 kg seed ha ⁻¹) + 1 hand weeding	20 (1993) 30 (1994)	-	-	2.5	432	0.98	247	-	-	-	-
				-	-	-	-	5.4	562	0.93	87
Pretilachlor + safener	3	0.4	30 EC ^b	3.7	392	1.23	305	3.7	512	0.99	563
Pretilachlor + safener	6	0.4	30 EC	2.6	378	0.93	430	-	-	-	-
Pretilachlor + safener	3	0.6	30 EC	4.7	400	1.06	225	4.4	463	1.06	304
Pretilachlor + safener	6	0.6	30 EC	4.6	385	1.39	267	-	-	-	-
Butachlor + safener	3	1.0	50 EC	3.4	322	1.22	279	3.4	484	0.87	678
Butachlor + safener	6	1.0	50 EC	3.0	358	1.08	394	-	-	-	-
Butachlor + safener	3	1.5	50 EC	3.6	373	1.07	422	4.1	498	0.89	357
Butachlor + safener	6	1.5	50 EC	4.0	355	1.16	404	-	-	-	-
Butachlor	3	1.0	50 EC	-	-	-	-	3.8	440	0.90	376
Butachlor	3	1.5	50 EC	3.4	389	1.30	305	3.4	425	0.85	444
Butachlor	6	1.5	50 EC	3.0	429	1.13	373	-	-	-	-
Anilophos	3	0.3	30 EC	-	-	-	-	1.5	244	0.69	601
Anilophos	3	0.4	30 EC	-	-	-	-	0.9	141	1.31	960
Anilophos	8	0.4	30 EC	3.7	391	1.15	360	3.5	355	1.05	356
Thiobencarb	3	1.0	50 EC	-	-	-	-	2.2	250	1.15	607
Thiobencarb	3	1.5	50 EC	-	-	-	-	1.9	202	1.06	678
Weedy (nonweeded control)	-	-	-	1.2	252	0.99	473	0.8	150	0.78	935
LSD (5%)				1.1	97	ns	200	1.5	150	0.34	213
CV (%)				21.0	18	26.00	46	23.0	28	24.00	31

^aDAS = days after seeding. ^bEC = emulsifiable concentrate.

weeds in direct seeded rice more effectively.

A field experiment was conducted during the 1993-94 wet season at the Crop Research Centre, Pantnagar (29 °N, 79 °E, 244 m altitude). Soil is silt loam (Aquic Hapludoll) with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, 0.1 % total N, and CEC 20 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil. The treatments (see table) were tested in a randomized block design with four replications. Short-duration variety Govind (90 d) was used in 1993 and Saket 4 (110 d) was planted in 1994. Pregeminated seeds were uniformly broadcast in puddled soil at 100 kg dry seeds ha⁻¹ on 10 Jul 1993 and 2 Jul 1994. A single dose of 18 kg P ha⁻¹ and 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹ was applied along with three splits of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ (1/2 as basal dressing, 1/4 at tillering, and 1/4 at panicle initiation). Soil was kept near saturation during seedling establishment and was later flooded with 0-5 cm water.

Weed samples were taken from a 0.25-m² area and were dried at 70 ± 5 °C. Dry weights were recorded. The common weeds found were *Echinochloa colona*, *Panicum* sp., *Digitaria* sp., *Cyperus iria*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Commelina henghalensis*, *Casulia axillaris*, and *Eclipta prostrata*. Grain yield was recorded from a 6-m² net plot area. Plant samples from 0.5 m² were taken at harvest to evaluate yield components.

Phytotoxicity problems were not observed in treatments with the new herbicide formulation (herbicides with safener). Weeds were controlled effectively in both years. Pretilachlor + safener at 0.6 kg ai ha⁻¹ applied 3 d after sowing was found most effective in controlling weeds. Yield was statistically at par with that of weed-free check and that of the crop that received two hand weedings. Compared with butachlor- and thiobencarb-treated plots, high plant density with one manual weeding at 30 d was found to suppress weeds significantly (see table). ■

Integrated pest management—other pests

Effect of soil solarization of rice nursery beds to suppress plant parasitic nematodes

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An advantage of solarizing nursery beds, aside from a favorable cost-benefit ratio, is its potential to suppress other soilborne pests besides the target pest. We explored the possibility of using this nonchemical method to suppress plant parasitic nematodes that infect rice seedlings.

Table 1. Effect of solarization and organic amendments on growth characters of rice seedlings. New Delhi, India.

Treatment	Length (cm)		Weight [g]	
	Shoot	Root	Shoot	Root
Control	26.20	6.70	0.42	0.165
Solarization	39.30	13.80	1.22	0.631
Organic amendment	38.40	14.80	1.39	0.644
SE ±	1.31	0.78	0.11	ns
LSD (5%)	2.75	1.65	0.23	ns

The experiment used a randomized block design and was conducted in the IARI farm during the 1995 summer season. The beds were infested with moderate to heavy population of plant parasitic nematodes, mostly root-knot nematodes *Meloidogyne* spp. Tillage was achieved by digging to a depth of about 10 cm, followed by light irrigation. Mulching was done with 60 µm-thick, transparent, white polyethylene sheet buried on all sides. Daily temperature was recorded for each treatment at 0800 and 1500 h for the entire 3-wk duration of solarization and organic amendment treatments. The organic amendment treatment consisted of incorporating mustard cake (0.5% w/w) into the soil 15 d prior to sowing of rice seeds.

At the end of the solarization treatment, polyethylene mulch was removed and soil samples at 0-15 cm depth were drawn. The modified sieving and decanting method by Cobb was used to extract nematodes from 150 cm³ of soil sample.

The nursery beds were loosened and irrigated; seeds of rice cultivar Basmati 370 were then sown. Seedlings were harvested 30 d after sowing and data on plant growth characters and nematode population in the soil were recorded.

Table 2. Effect of solarization and organic amendment on population of nematodes infecting rice seedlings. New Delhi, India.

Nematode species	Nematode population 250 cm ³ of soil		Percentage Increase/decrease ^a
	Pre-treatment	Post-treatment	
<i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.			
Control	172	250	45.3 (+)
Solarization	115	15	87.0 (-)
Organic amendment	116	33	71.5 (-)
<i>Helicotylenchus</i> spp.			
Control	13	33	153.8 (-)
Solarization	71	30	57.7 (-)
Organic amendment	41	23	43.9 (-)
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i> spp.			
Control	23	40	74.0 (+)
Solarization	61	25	59.0 (-)
Organic amendment	33	22	33.3 (-)
<i>Pratylenchus</i> spp.			
Control	26	45	73.0 (+)
Solarization	37	18	51.3 (-)
Organic amendment	14	7	50.0 (-)
<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>			
Control	105	139	32.4 (+)
Solarization	56	13	76.8 (-)
Organic amendment	78	57	27.0 (-)

^a+ = increase; - = decrease.